

Management

ACHIEVING HIGH PRODUCTIVITY AND QUALITY BY WORKING AS A TEAM-WORK IN THE ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract

Increasing productivity is one of the most critical goals in an organization. Also the quality of the markets is an important target that many experienced managers who emphasize the merits of "good teamwork" have numerous behavioral requirements in mind. Their claims remain rather vague and meaningless, however, as long as the essence of a team, the quality of its collaborative working, is neither precisely defined nor validly and reliably measured and that explain which aspects of teamwork are relevant to team performance and then testing these propositions to make distinctions that are useful for particular purposes. This paper will explain mission and objectives of organizations with the strategies of the organizations and the external and internal analysis which include Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats factors. The objectives are developed in line with the management, communication skills, boosting employees' morale, strategic planning and achieving high productivity and quality are what the members of the team should know. To work as a team, the organization must teach its employees' on the process that could lead towards achieving their objectives. These could be in terms of how they should prepare, how to temper emotion towards achieving the organization objectives.

Keywords: Team-Work; Organizations; Goals And Objectives.

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1. Introduction

The purpose of assembling a team is to group together individuals that have specific skills to accomplish a specific project. The purpose in which an individual is selected is based on their skills specifically evaluating overall team and system process effectiveness when putting a team together (Brooks-Buza & Fernandez and Stenger, 2011). The first step in developing a cohesive team is careful selection of team members. When selecting team members, companies should take care to pair workers with peers, they get along well with. If workers are placed with individuals they fight with or cannot work cooperatively with, the teams will likely not prove

successful. For a team to be cohesive, the members that fill it must trust each other. Managers can promote trust by arranging trust-building exercises or encouraging employees to develop relationships that extend beyond the workplace, creating bonds between the members that fill the team.

For teams to function cohesively, all members must clearly understand the team objectives. Developing an objective is the first task that teams should undertake. After deciding upon an ultimate goal, workers will be better able to function cooperatively to work toward that goal. Communication is a key in successful team building. A group processes within the team and the nature of the work itself (Campion et al., 1993; Gladstein, 1984). Managers who oversee teams should encourage their workers to communicate regularly with each other. They may also develop methods to aid in their communication, such as setting up email lists that the members of the team can use to communicate with ease. While managers may want to create cohesive teams that are largely autonomous, it is still necessary to keep tabs on them. Managers can promote the development of cohesive teams by encouraging their workers to give feedback on the functioning of the team and organizational performance is improved through teamwork (Montes, and Moreno & Morales, 2005). If they learn through this feedback that something within the team needs to be modified, they can act quickly to keep their teams functioning well.

The many experienced managers who emphasize the merits of "good teamwork" have numerous behavioral requirements in mind. Their claims remain rather vague and meaningless, however, as long as the essence of a team, the quality of its collaborative working, is neither precisely defined nor validly and reliably measured. I advocate first developing theories that explain which aspects of teamwork are relevant to team performance and then testing these propositions to make distinctions that are useful for particular purposes. Following the work of Homans (1974) on the elementary forms of social behavior, we can conceptualize human behavior in teams as activities, interactions, and sentiments. Activities are observable actions of individuals that can be measured by quantity (e.g., the production output of a factory worker) as well as by the correctness of their execution (e.g. the effectiveness of an action). It refers to the connectedness or the "being in contact" of two or more people regardless of the activities that bring them into contact. According to Homans (1974) interaction can be studied in terms of frequency and intensity. The third element of social behavior is 56% timing which refers to human emotions, motivations, or attitudes. Sentiments cannot be directly observed, but nevertheless influence interactions and activities and are in turn, influenced by them. The focus of this research is solely on the quality of interactions within teams rather than team members" (task) activities. Starting from the widespread fundamental proposition that the success of work conducted, teams depends (beyond the quantity and correctness of the task activities) on how well team members collaborate or interact.

2. Mission and Objectives of an Organization

For every organization to function well, it must clearly state their mission and the objectives that they want to achieve.

2.1.Missions

The mission statements are critically important for an organization as it describes to all stakeholders its strengths, purposes, and goals/objectives. The strategic management process requires the establishment of an organizational direction which typically first requires the creation of an accurate mission statement. Organizations rely on their mission to attract resources and guide decision-making. The mission is more than a statement or a symbol; it is a tool that provides a clear, compelling statement of purpose that is disseminated both internally and externally. According to Sheehan (1996) has studied philanthropic organizations and concluded that although most had clear statements of mission, very few had developed performance measurement systems.

Increasingly mission statements are recognized as a strong management tool that can motivate employees and keep them focused on the purpose of the organization. Often times, the mission statement attracts clients, donors, funders, employees, and volunteers to a nonprofit organization and gain coherence and focus in pursuit of their mission (Kaplan, 2011). Reliance on the mission as a management tool is recognized as an effective strategy to improve performance in many organizations.

2.2.Objectives

The overall goal and mission of a business that have been established by its management and communicated to its employees. The organizational objectives of a company typically focus on its long range intentions for operating and its overall business philosophy that can provide useful guidance for employees seeking to please their managers. The strategic objectives were to create value for the company, the had to be translated into tangible goals and actions (Kaplan, 1996). Among the areas to be consider when developing organization objectives are:

- **Management Development:**

Discover effective ways to get tasks accomplished through others. Develop your next line of leaders and see what they can accomplish through effective delegation

- **Communication Skills:**

Promoting a two-way system of communication between the supervisors and the employees for clarifying expectations about the roles and accountabilities, communicating the functional and organizational goals, providing a regular and a transparent feedback for improving employee performance and continuous coaching. Learn to set clear objectives and measure performance.

- **Boosting Employee Morale:**

Boosting the employee's performance, by encouraging employee's empowerment, motivation and implementation of an effective reward mechanism. The overcoming obstacles to the team's morale will soar. Discover how having fun and accomplishing goals can be the best morale booster around. Promoting personal growth and advancement in the career of the employees' by helping them in acquiring the desired knowledge and skills (Wheelen & Hunger, 2011).

- **Strategic Planning:**

Discover how to structure your planning time to produce maximum results. Learn how to avoid the planning pitfalls that every leader faces. Learn guidelines for keeping the team focused on productive planning.

3. Achieve High Productivity and Quality

Increasing productivity is one of the most critical goals in an organization. Also the quality of the markets is an important target. Goals and Objectives in Planning

(Wheelen & Hunger, 2011)

4. Team Work

Consider the definition of management by Mary Parker; she defined “management as getting things done through other peoples”. In today’s world, almost everything is accomplished by teams. Large companies often use project teams that span the global capital market, small companies use teams to ensure their products and services reach their customers. Consequently, teamwork has become an essential aspect of practice (White, 1999). A team environment is any setting that requires two or more people to work together toward the accomplishment of a task. Whatever role you prefer to fill, whether alone or with others, it is likely that you will occasionally encounter situations that call for team work. It’s important for employees to understand who in the group will have specific responsibilities. This often means giving up recognition for overall benefit of the team.

Considering the background of the story between the Tortoise and Hare, they are working in the same environment, trying to compete in order to achieve the organization’s target, but they missed the processes that supposed to follow. This is because to achieve an organization objective in a team, there must be process to be followed.

5. Process of Team Work

While the actual tasks involved in teamwork vary from organization to organization and also from task to task, there are three main processes that are common to teamwork in an organization. Each of these three processes involves specific action. These are:

- a) Transition process
- b) Action process
- c) Inter personal process

6. Transition Process

This occurs before a project begins or before new projects get started. The following stages need to be followed:

- **Mission Analysis**

An organizations' mission is the purpose or reason for the organization's existence. It tells what company is providing to society-either service such as house cleaning or a product such as automobile. A well-conceived mission statement defines the fundamental, unique purpose that sets a company apart from other firms of its type and identifies the scope or domain of the company's operations in terms of products including services offered and markets served (wheelen and hunger, 2011).

Research reveals that firms with mission statements containing explicit descriptions of customers served and technologies used have significantly higher growth than firms without such statements. An example of a broad mission statement is that used by many corporations: "serve the best interests of share owners, customers, and employees.

- **Goal Specification**

These are the end results of planned activity. They should be stated as action verbs and tell what is to be accomplished by when and quantified if possible. The achievement of corporate objectives should result in the fulfilment of a corporation's mission.

- **Strategy Formulation**

A strategy of an organization forms a comprehensive master plan that states how the organization will achieve its mission and objectives. However, strategy formulation often referred to as strategic planning or long-range planning, is concerned with developing a corporation's mission, objectives, strategies, and policies. It begins with situation analysis: the process of finding a strategic fit between external opportunities and internal strengths while working around external threats and internal weaknesses.

7. Action Process

This occurs while the team is completing necessary tasks. The stages under this process are:

- **Monitoring goals**

In this case, organization's sought to "measures what is measurable". These measures are usually set out in what are referred to as key performance indicators. In order to check on the success of continuous improvement, it is important to have a number of measures in place so that the goals of an organization's can be achieved

- **Monitoring Systems and Processes**

The management of an organization on the process of the activities or steps needed to accomplish in a single use plan. It makes a strategy action oriented which may involve restructuring the company's internal culture, or beginning a new research effort.

- **Coordination**

This is the act of synchronization and integration of organization's activities, responsibilities, and command and control structures of strategic goals to ensure that resources of an organization are used in most effective and efficient pursuit of the objectives.

8. Interpersonal Process

This occurs during the transition and action process. This process also has the following stages to be follow:

A. Conflict Resolution: - Understanding and appreciating the various viewpoints involved in conflict are key factors in its resolution. These are the key skills for all team members to develop. To resolve conflict in an organization the following stages should be considered:

- i. **Avoid trying to be the team leader:** Remember that everyone on your team has a role. Being part of a team environment means recognizing your role, as well as understanding the value of everyone else's roles, so you may all integrate your roles for the purpose of accomplishing the team goal. Common roles include:
 - The technician is the person who assumes thorough knowledgeable about the task and process, and is a good source of useful information and practical guidance.
 - The innovator is the creative person on the team, and is good at conceptualizing new ideas, as well as out-of-the-box problem solving.
 - The motivator is the team player who keeps everyone on task by way of a positive attitude and openness to whatever it takes to get the job done.
- ii. **Take turns:** It is important that everyone on the team is heard. In order to be a team player, you must respect that all team members, as well as what they have to say, are equally important. When someone else is speaking, wait your turn and, conversely, when you are speaking, look for acknowledgments from your team members that what you are saying is understood.
- iii. **Use "we" language:** Building team-work skills involves learning non-confrontational approaches to communication. You may do this by substituting "we" for "you" and "I" in your statements. For example, you may rephrase the confrontational phrase, "you were supposed to figure that out," in a way that is non-confrontational by saying something more like, "we need to resolve this issue"
- iv. **Contribute positive feedback.** Boosting and maintaining a positive morale in the team environment is the responsibility of every team member. Foster this practice by encouraging your team members, approaching projects with a positive, can-do mindset and inspiring others with your attitude.
- v. **Take time to get to know each of your team mates:** Remember that no two people are alike, and that each team player has strengths, weaknesses, likes and dislikes. Knowing what makes your teammates tick is necessary to developing strong and productive working relationships, and to learning how to complement each other's job roles
- vi. **Act Selflessly:** Consider the equal importance of everyone on the team environment before you make a decision. For example, it would be inconsiderate to be the first to

- leave in the evening and the last to arrive to work every day, just because you can. Additionally, it may be necessary at times to compensate for the sickness or personal crisis of another team player without thinking about how it is negatively affecting you.
- vii. **Treat others on your team as you would want to be treated:** Before you speak or act, ask yourself how you would feel if one of your teammates spoke or acted in that way, and then use that insight for building team work.
 - viii. **Take time to get to know each of your team mates:** Remember that no two people are alike, and that each team player has strengths, weaknesses, likes and dislikes. Knowing what makes your teammates tick is necessary to developing strong and productive working relationships, and to learning how to complement each other's job roles
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 - x. **Treat others on your team as you would want to be treated:** Before you speak or act, as yourself how you would feel if 1 of your teammates spoke or acted in that way, then use that insight for building team work.

B. Motivation and Configuration Development: In this situation, the company can create a work environment in which employee are motivated about work. This involves both intrinsically satisfying and extrinsically encouraging factors.

Going back to the story, which said that the moral of story is slow and steady, wins the race. This referred to a situation where in an organization employees are pushed to perform faster and, in many environments, we are rewarded for speed. However, it is very difficult, if not impossible to achieve the right objectives on targeted time if we are not clear on what success really looks like on the resources required, and a plan. Taking time to prepare and identify a strategy to achieve success will prevent truly detrimental detailers, and in turn, help to beat our deadlines. Considering what happens between those two employees i.e., the Tortoise and Hare, after several consultation and competition, the targeted aim is to win the race. Since they follow the above mentioned teamwork process, the end version is to achieve (win the race).

9. How to Work in a Team to Achieve Your Goals

The organization goals can be achieving by considering the following:

- **Gets ready to achieve:** - sometimes the most valuable action we can take is waiting extra time to gather what we need, ask questions, gather additional materials, fill in the critical spots where we need more data. Be sure to find out about procedures, policies, politics, or strategies before we create our plan. Taking all available working knowledge and funnelling it into a series of steps and procedures to create a positive outcome. When planning and organizing, it is vital to gather all the available knowledge we can have about our initiative.
- **Temper Emotion:** - As human being powered by emotions and energy can be fantastic, where energy can launch to quickly achieve milestone and blow through any obstacles. Invariably, though, emotion can only take us to our team so far and may start slowing

down and then obstacle or situation comes along that stop us dead in our track: money runs out.

- **Success:** - To avoid hitting this wall, begin by mapping out an initiation for the department organization spends a couple of extra days or weeks, if you have it, to organize the business knowledge that will inform and strengthen the planning process.

10. Roles Appropriate in Teamwork

There are eight roles which guide to appropriate in the useful of teamwork identified by Billin. These are:

- **Chairman** - Focuses on objectives; establishes the work roles and boundaries for other team members. Shows concern to use human resources effectively. Clarifies and sets agendas. Summarizes and makes decisions when necessary, a good listener and communicator.
- **Shaper** - High nervous energy. Full of enthusiasm and drive. Continually looking for opportunities for action from ideas. Heavily involved in team's action and successes. The task leader of the group.
- **Plant** - The creative ideas person; tends to bring new insight and imagination to the group. Concerned with basics, not details. Tends to criticize. May withdraw if ideas are rejected.
- **Monitor-evaluator** - Objective and serious concerned with idea analysis rather than idea generation. May lack motivation, but skilled in analysis and decision making.
- **Company worker** - The practical organizer. Concerned with order and feasibility. Methodical, efficient and systematic. Does not respond well to innovation or lack of structure. Pragmatically focused; may be inflexible, but responds to direction.
- **Resource investigator** - Friendly and sociable; enthusiastic and positive. The member who goes outside the team to explore and obtain new ideas and information. Enthusiasm may fade quickly; tends to be stimulated by others.
- **Team worker** - Sensitive, aware of feelings and emotions in the group. Tends to weld the team together. A popular and supportive member; uncompetitive and dislikes friction. A good listener and communicator.
- **Completer-finisher** - Concerned with details and order, tends to worry over possible mistakes; communicates a permanent sense of urgency. May get bogged down in detail, losing sight of the main objective.

11. The Strategy of the Organization

Keep Communication, Open Promote Trust, Encourage Feedback the most common users of a SWOT analysis are team members and project managers who are responsible for decision making and strategic planning (Hunger & Wheelen, 2014). The SWOT analysis in organisation categories into two; that is, internal and external analysis (A. Pressman, 2006).

- **Internal Analysis:** The internal analysis considers the organisation's resources (both financial and human) and its "distinct (or core) competencies". A common and simple tool for this, is the SWOT analysis. The internal factors are Strength and Weaknesses (Wheelen & Hunger, 2015) . To determine the internal factors, the following questions must be considered.

<u>Strengths</u>	<u>Weaknesses</u>
Advantages of proposition?	Disadvantages of proposition?
Capabilities?	Gaps in capabilities?
Competitive advantages?	Lack of competitive strength?
Marketing - reach, distribution, awareness?	Reputation, presence and reach?
Innovative aspects?	Financials?
Location and geographical?	Own known vulnerabilities?
Price, value, quality?	Timescales, deadlines and pressures?
Accreditation, qualifications, certifications?	Reliability of data, plan predictability?
USP's (unique selling points)?	Morale, commitment, leadership?
Resources, Assets, People?	Accreditation?
Experience, knowledge, data?	Cash flow, start-up cash-drain?
Financial reserves, likely returns?	Continuity, supply chain robustness?
Processes, systems, IT, communications?	Effects on core activities, distraction?
Cultural, attitudinal, behavioral?	Processes and systems?
Management cover, succession?	Management cover, succession?

- **External Analysis:** This considers the organization's outside environment with a common sample tool for Opportunities and Threat (Frynas, et al, 2006). The external factors to be considered are:

<u>Opportunities</u>	<u>Threats</u>
Market developments?	Political effects
Competitors' vulnerabilities	Legislative effects
New USP's	Obstacles faced
Tactics - surprise, major contracts	Insurmountable weaknesses
Business and product development	Environmental effects
Information and research	IT developments
Partnerships, agencies, distribution	Competitor intentions - various
Industry or lifestyle trends	Loss of key staff
Technology development and innovation	Sustainable financial backing
Global influences	Market demand
New markets, vertical, horizontal	New technologies, services, ideas
Niche target markets	Vital contracts and partners
Geographical, export, import	Sustaining internal capabilities
Volumes, production, economies	Economy - home, abroad
Seasonal, weather, fashion influences	

The success of any group project is that there must be a clear single goal. Many teams fail when there are multiple agendas (Kambil et al, 2002). Teams and organizations that succeed are those that have communicated a common purpose and goal.

With all communication clarity is a must. Great communication keeps team members from aborting the core of the project due to lack of understanding of the overall purpose (Bigness et al, 1995). Frequent communication of the project purpose can be vital in keeping the team on track.

12. You have got to talk to Each Other

Not only the communication of the project goal is vital, but frequent updates of the task are important. With multiple tools at our fingertips like email, mobile phones, wiki's, and project management software, to not communicate is a sure sign of lack of commitment from team members.

13. Everyone Cannot Lead

Every task must have a project lead. There are many ways to choose a leader. Some managers choose to select by an individual's area of expertise or their ability to communicate and manage projects and people. The ideal situation is to delegate to an individual that is skilled in both areas.

14. Conclusions

Working in a team in every organization leads to successful achievement of their objectives. The success of every organization depends on how the mission and objectives of that organization communicate to the team members (employees') in order to have goal congruence, whereby the objectives of the organization are in line with the employees' objectives. Missions are the tool that provides a clear, compelling statement of purpose that is disseminated both internally and externally in an organization. While, the objectives are developed in line with the management, communication skills, boosting employees' morale, strategic planning and achieving high productivity and quality are what the members of the team should know. To work as a team, the organization must teach its employees' on the process that could lead towards achieving their objectives. These could be in terms of how they should prepare, how to temper emotion towards achieving the organization objectives.

SWOT analysis is also used by team members and managers for decision making. This could be used to determine the internal factors within an organization which could refer to the Strength and Weakness, and external factors, known as Opportunities and Threat. It's good to be individually brilliant and to have strong core competencies; but unless you are able to work in a team and harness each other's core competencies, you will always perform below par because there will always be situations at which you will do poorly and someone in a team does well, in that situation he can guide you to a proper way.

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